

Current Competency Status Of The Teacher Team Being Personnel- In-Charge Of The Ho Chi Minh Young Pioneer Organization (Hypo) In Vietnam

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Current Status, Competency Or Competencies, Teacer Or Teachers, Personnel- In-Charge.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5071277</p>	<p><i>In 2018, in order to implement the Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW (Resolution of the Central Committee of the Vietnamese Communist Party of Vietnam), Ministry of Education and Training of Vietnam issued the General Education Program, which aims to help "teachers promote their initiative and creativity in implementing the program". In order to achieve this goal, teachers in general and teachers being personnel-in-charge of Ho Chi Minh Young Pioneer Organization need to have the necessary qualifications to perform the task well. Therefore, finding out the current competency status of the teacher team being personnel-in-charge of the Ho Chi Minh Youth Pioneer Organization (HYPO) as a basis for building a competency framework for teacher team being personnel-in-charge of HYPO in order to meet the requirements of the general education program in the current period. The study identified 06 core competency groups and conducted a survey on 160 teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge in 4 provinces (cities): Ho Chi Minh City, Hanoi City, Ninh Thuan Province and Kien Giang province.</i></p>

Introduction

In the Resolution No.29-NQ/TW stipulated "On the requirements of fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training to meet the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the context of a socialist-oriented market economy and international integration" of the 8th Central Conference (Session XI) directed many contents, including setting the task of "Standardizing the teaching staff according to each educational level and training level. In recent years, the country is in the period of industrialization - modernization to integrate with the world. Therefore, education is facing the challenge of innovating and improving the quality of staff - including teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge in schools. For many different reasons such as: term of duty, in parallel with being personnel-in-charge is professional duties, remuneration regime or skills of practicing professional activities of the HYPO's personnel-in-charge, etc are the problems that the HYPO's personnel-in-charge have to overcome in order to perform well their functions and tasks.

The Government assigned the Ministry of Education and Training to issue a list of job positions in educational institutions, according to which, each public non-business unit (educational institution) must complete a scheme on job positions at the unit, which includes a description of the competency framework of the positions. On the basis of the description and competency framework, managers of units have appropriate grounds to recruit, employ, manage, train and foster in order to maximize the effectiveness of the use of human resources. However, the actual education and training career at pedagogical schools today shows that pedagogical students have little or no formal training in Youth Union, Association and Organization work. With the current training program, the question is whether the graduates from the pedagogical universities participating in recruitment for the position of the HYPO's personnel-in-charge at educational institutions can meet the requirements on knowledge, profession, skills (basic issues of professional competence) to perform assigned tasks.

Determining the necessary competencies of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge is a necessary work because it both serves the competency framework and job position in accordance with regulations and clearly defines the core competencies of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge. In addition, only when the specific competencies and suitable competencies for being HYPO's personnel-in-charge in schools, then can we design education, training and fostering programs, and look for teachers who have been on professional duties, while performing the duties of the HYPO's personnel-in-charge.

Based on the concept of competencies in general, the competencies of teachers and the work characteristics of HYPO's personnel-in-charge in schools, we believe that: the competencies of teachers being

personnel-in-charge are those of teachers to perform the work of HYPO's personnel-in-charge. The competencies of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge includes 02 groups of competencies: the competencies to be a teacher and the competencies to be a HYPO's personnel-in-charge in the school (general and specific competencies - professional competencies to be in charge of the work).

From the theory of elements constituting professional competencies or competence, we believe that it is the combination of knowledge, professional skills, specialized skills in the Youth Team's work and attitude of love for the profession, love the children, and passionate enthusiasm in Team's work and children's movements, passion in social activities are indispensable factors and constitute the competency framework of a teacher acts as a HYPO's personnel-in-charge.

Within the scope of this article, we only examine the specific competencies and competencies of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge, which consists of 06 specific capacities:

- **Competency (ability) to understand others:** competency (ability) of the teacher acts as a HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have basic knowledge of other people's psychological characteristics and be able to give appropriate behavior to achieve effective result to obtain high efficiency during his or her task performance.

- **Competency (ability) to understand guidelines and policies related to professional activities:** the competency (ability) of a teacher who is a HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have basic knowledge about guidelines and policies for the professional field from which to apply the right, appropriate and flexible ways to achieve high efficiency in the process of performing tasks.

- **Decision-making and problem-solving competency:** the competency (ability) of a teacher who is a HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have basic knowledge of identifying problems that are being encountered, thereby applying his or her own knowledge and experience to solve problems effectively and bring success to work.

- **Competency (ability) to self-realize professional skills and expertise:** the competency (ability) of a teacher who is a HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have basic knowledge and skills about the HYPO's work. On the other hand, you can do it yourself and guide the members the skills of the HYPO's work.

- **Competency (ability) to organize activities in the HYPO's work:** the competency (ability) of a teacher who is a HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have basic knowledge about the HYPO's activities and be able to organize activities to help the team members to train and develop their personalities.

- **Competency (ability) to coordinate with forces in organizing activities:** the competency (ability) of a teacher who is a HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have a basic understanding of the functions and tasks of the forces in the school so that from there plan to coordinate closely to implement and organize HYPO's activities successfully.

1.2. Study (research) purposes

Study (research) on the current competency status of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge in the current period.

1.3. Histories of the study (research) case.

1.3.1. A number of studies on competencies and competency framework

In the world and in the country, there are many study (research) works on competencies and competency framework of certain fields. Typically: competency framework of leaders - managers, competency frameworks for teachers or competency frameworks in different career fields. However, currently there is not a comprehensive and systematic study on the competency framework of HYPO's personnel-in-charge position. Because, the field of Union, Association and Organization is a typical field in Vietnam. Researchers around the world have little or no research in this field. Therefore, in the process of studying the Competency Framework for the Organization's personnel-in-charge, previous studies on the Competency Framework were only used as a theoretical basis, for reference only to contribute to the building of the Competency Framework of the Organization's personnel-in-charge.

Ph. N. Gonobolin wrote in "Psychological qualities of a teacher" - volume 1, Education Publishing House, 1976: "Capabilities are individual psychological attributes of the individual, thanks to these attributes that people complete well a certain activity". Competency appears and develops in the process of operation. Competency is different from skill in that: skill is the result of practice and learning, but also to develop competencies, in addition, it is necessary to have character, that is, the physiological and anatomical characteristics of the people's nervous system. The attributes we call competencies are also developed on the natural basis of those characteristics. However, competencies are formed and developed in the process of operation, associated with human knowledge and skills. The more people know about a certain field, the more their activities in this area developed [Ph. N. Gonobolin (1976)].

P.A. Rudich (1980) in his book named "*Psychology*" gave a definition of competency: "Human competencies and psycho-physiological properties govern the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, techniques as well as effectiveness in performance of a certain activity". This definition has expanded the concept of competencies to include psycho-physiological conditions that govern human activities [P.A. Rudich, 1980]

In the research work on "Studying and building a competency framework of cadres and civil servants in Can Tho city", author Nguyen Hong Tin and his colleagues have clearly pointed out that the competency framework is a resonance between the following factors: competencies, core competencies, specialized competencies etc ...In addition, the authors also point out the theoretical basis for building a competency framework for public cadres and civil servants, etc. In which, the author focuses on building a competency framework based on DFID (2010), including: DFID (2010) identify each group of core competencies including three main components: competency, competency descriptor and behavioral indicators [Nguyen Hong Tin, 2015].

With the same research direction and research viewpoints, author Le Quan and his colleagues in the research project "Research and application of competency frameworks in human resource development for leadership and management in the Northwest region" also pointed out important grounds for building a competency framework based on the studies of Western countries. In which, it also mentions the basic elements to form a competency framework such as knowledge, skills, and attitudes. These three aspects are divided into two groups: core competencies and specialized competencies.

Author Bui Hong Quan and his colleagues also mentioned the competency framework, the author said that: The competency framework is a popular governance model in the world since the 1990s and recently, some countries in the European Asia and Southeast Asia have also implemented the application of competency frameworks to attract and improve the quality of human resources in the public sector. However, in Vietnam in general, and Ho Chi Minh City in particular, there is little interest in this. Therefore, the study of the leadership and management competency framework and showing the current competencies of the leadership and management staff is a work with scientific and practical significance [Bui Hong Quan et al. , 2019].

1.3.2. Some studies on the role of the HYPO's personnel-in-charge in schools

In the study: "Improving the quality of the training and fostering teachers cum HYPO's personnel-in-charge in the current period (2014), author Nguyen Minh Thai said that the HYPO's current personnel-in-charge has not been trained and fostered methodically, scientifically and intensively, so it has more or less greatly influenced the quality of the Organization's work and the children's movement in schools today. With his research results, the author believes that if there are solutions to link the management agencies and the training and fostering programs are implemented in a more methodical, scientific and professional manner, they will increase the competencies of the Organization's personnel-in-charge. This is the practical basis to orient the development to build the competency framework of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge, to provide a system of scientific, objective and appropriate solutions to the actual situation.

Author Nguyen Thai An, in his research work named "The current situation of training, fostering and using teachers who are the Organization's personnel-in-charge in schools in 2016", has made a general assessment of the quality of teachers who are the Organization's personnel-in-charge. In which, the author focused on surveying on professional qualifications, trained specialties and some issues related to the ability to perform the duties of a teacher who are the Organization's personnel-in-charge. The results of this study also show that most of the current team being HYPO's personnel-in-charge have little specialized training, expertise and skills related to professional activities. Teachers working as the Organization's personnel-in-charge are only allowed to learn a small amount of knowledge and skills in pedagogical schools, then most teachers often follow the motto "training-on-the-job". Therefore, the quality of Organization's activities in schools has not been improved [Nguyen Thai An, 2017].

In summary, we realize that every career field must have the necessary competencies. This competency system is typical of each industry or profession. In order to participate in the professional field, it is necessary to have the corresponding competencies and must meet the competencies of the profession. Most of the research works focus on analyzing the general competencies of some job positions but have not mentioned the competencies of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge. These studies have all shown the skills and professions of the person in charge of the job that must be performed in the course of performing the task. In order to perform well the functions and duties of the person-in-charge, the person-in-charge of the position needs to be well-trained, regularly fostered, and must have an environment in which to demonstrate his or her abilities or competencies.

2. Research Methods

- Main objects: 160 teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge.
- Research sample selection method: The research topic focuses on the study of the Organization's personnel-in-charge in the cities and provinces: Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh, Ninh Thuan and Kien Giang. In order to ensure objectivity and ensure the appropriate research sample, the study selected random samples distributed by regions: North, Central and South regions, specifically in the following table:

Table 2.1. Distribution of the study samples

No	Regions	Quantity	%
1	Kien Giang	40	25
2	Ho Chi Minh City	40	25

3	Ninh Thuan	40	25
4	Ha Noi	40	25
Total		160	100%

- Research method: Investigate by questionnaire to find out the contents related to the problem of performance expression of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge and use SPSS software to process collected data. In addition, the study (research) used the method of in-depth interviews with a number of objects who are teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge and administrators in several schools.

- Scoring method: The study is based on the results from the obtained questionnaire of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge.

Table 2.2: Competence assessment of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge.

No	Average score	Level
1	1.00 – 1.75	Low
2	1.76 – 2.50	Medium
3	2.51 – 3.25	High
4	3.26 – 4.00	Very high

3. Research results and discussion

3.1. Current competency status of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge

Study to analyze each component competency in the competency framework of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge according to the given study criteria, the study will show the frequency of selecting different levels of competency assessment. The teacher's competencies who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge by percentage in order to assess the overall selection of the objects to have an overview of the current competency status of HYPO's personnel-in-charge. In addition, we also give an overview of the Grade Point Average (GPA) results of the competency groups so that the assessment results are objective and general about the competency study issue of teachers being Ho Chi Minh Young Pioneer Organization (HYPO) in the current period.

Table 3.1: Current competency status of teachers acts as HYPO's personnel-in-charge

No.	Competencies	Results		
		GPA	Standard deviation points (SD)	Rating
1	Ability to understand others	2.98	0.62	3
2	Ability to understand guidelines and policies related to professional activities	3.06	0.63	1
3	Decision making and problem solving abilities	3.04	0.63	2
4	Ability to self-implement professional operation and skills	2.83	0.66	5
5	Ability to organize activities in HYPO's work	2.76	0.69	6
6	Ability to coordinate with forces in organizing activities	2.92	0.63	4
GPA		2,93		

According to the results in Table 3.1, it shows that there is a difference in the Grade Point Average (GPA) between the competencies. A specific assessment of each competencies of teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge shows that of the six competencies, the ability to understand guidelines and policies related to professional activities, the ability to solve problems with the Grade Point Average (GPA) in the survey is 3.06 and 3.0, which is quite high in the evaluation criteria. Within the scope of this study, this competencies is considered as the ability to understand the policies of the Party and the State of the HYPO's personnel-in-charge position in the schools, the ability to solve problems with students, the management principal board, in charge and teachers in the school. In addition, this competencies also focuses on imparting knowledge of laws and policies related to pupils. Combined with the in-depth interview method to explain why this competency is well performed by the teacher who is HYPO's personnel-in-charge, Ms. P.M.L (Vice Principal of District 9 Secondary School, Ho Chi Minh City) said: "I myself have been in charge for a long time, so I have to understand the guidelines and policies of the law, understand to protect the children, and when asked by parents, I must know to answer, read the documents, information myself, have to please everyone, handle many situations and then become a skilled and proficient person when facing problems of pupils, or parents or the relationship between pupils and teachers then pupils always call me. However, to get these competencies, I also have to spend many years doing this work, but it is difficult for young personnel-in-charge to do because there is little time to invest, lack of experience and have not gone through good training schools or training courses specializing in the personnel-in-charge position".

Thus, it can be said that the results of the survey and in-depth interviews show that in order to obtain the competencies of teachers to be the HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have the ability to understand policies

and guidelines, they must regularly participate in training courses to foster competencies to understand legal policies and regularly participating in solving problems that occur in schools related to pupils will forge the team of HYPO's personnel-in-charge with more competencies to solve problems. In addition, it is the policy change to ensure the rights and responsibilities of teachers act as HYPO's personnel-in-charge. In the remaining 02 competencies, the ability to understand others and the ability to coordinate with the average score of 2.96 and 3.0, this is a good score in the rating scale. This result is related to the problem-solving competencies and understanding of the Party and State's policies and laws. This means that teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge to have the ability to solve problems related to guidelines and policies for the HYPO's personnel-in-charge in schools.

The above results show that the teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge, whether or not they perform well, are the ability to organize activities in the HYPO's personnel-in-charge's work and the ability to self-implement professional skills subjects with average scores of 2.76 and 2.83, respectively. These are two skills that have quite a big difference compared to the other abilities. This result proves the theoretical assessment of the practical competencies of teachers as HYPO's personnel-in-charge. We are focusing on building a legal framework, regulations on the responsibilities or rights of teachers as HYPO's personnel-in-charge, but we have not focused on designing and building fostering and training programs for teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge or the next generations.

Combined with the in-depth interview method, it also shows that when it comes to the ability to understand or implement policies, the teachers who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge have a very good competencies, but in terms of organizing activities in the HYPO's work, they only work at low results. Ms. N.T.M (Thai Van Lung Secondary School, Thu Duc, Ho Chi Minh City) said in the interview: *"Not everyone has the skills to organize the pleasant activities, I used to be a teacher due to lack of lessons, so I changed to acts as HYPO's personnel-in-charge. When I'm 40 years old, I don't have much interest in children's activities anymore, and because I can't keep up with their trends, so the operational organization is not good yet"*. This observation shows that the teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge are not properly trained and due to their old age, there are many difficulties in the process of organizing activities. In addition to the professional operation factors, the dynamism and creativity to well implement the movement is also a factor that needs attention. Therefore, the selection of teachers to be the HYPO's personnel-in-charge should also pay attention to this issue.

Chart 3.1. Compare the GPA of competency groups

In reality, the teachers being the HYPO's personnel-in-charge are randomly selected based on the volunteer spirit of the teachers who have passion and interest in the youth movement or on a compulsory basis for teachers who lack lesson hours. Because of this, the quality of HYPO's personnel-in-charge's activities and children's movements in schools is not good, there are disparities between this unit and others, between this area and other area. Therefore, it is necessary to build competency groups in the competency framework of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge to evaluate the teaching staff being HYPO's personnel-in-charge and arrange human resources suitable to the job position.

Thus, it can be said that in order to become a teacher who is HYPO's personnel-in-charge, strong in theory, professional and skilled, in addition to understanding the theory in the process of studying in class, it requires the HYPO's personnel-in-charge to improve their own practice and self-study. Training institutions for HYPO's personnel-in-charge should develop a competency framework suitable for the HYPO's personnel-in-charge's position in schools, which must be suitable for each region so that after entering professional practice schools, it can be implemented immediately. The initial survey results showed the assessment of 06 competencies of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge's position, which is most evident in the percentage and grade point average score of each competency group in the HYPO's personnel-in-charge's position based teacher's competency framework the current period.

3.2. Correlation between competency groups in the competency framework of teachers acting as HYPO's personnel-in-charge's position.

Table 3.2: Correlation between competency groups

	Ability to understand others	Ability to understand policy	Decision making ability	Self-actualization ability	Ability to organize activities	Ability to coordinate with forces
Ability to understand others	1	.643**	.544**	.641**	.670**	.917**
Ability to understand policy	.643**	1	.749**	.714**	.608**	.688**
Decision making ability	.544**	.749**	1	.627**	.636**	.618**
Self-actualization ability	.641**	.714**	.627**	1	.622**	.683**
Ability to organize activities	.670**	.608**	.636**	.622**	1	.729**
Ability to coordinate with forces	.917**	.688**	.618**	.683**	.729**	1

Figure 3.1: Correlation between competency groups

The results of table 3.2 and diagram 3.1 show that there is a positive and quite close relationship between the competencies, the above numbers are statistical. This shows that when one ability increased or decreased, it will affect other abilities to be increased or decreased. That means that a certain ability with low GPA will lead to the remaining capabilities with low GPA and vice versa.

When comparing the results of the pairs of correlations between competencies, there is a heterogeneous correlation. Competence pairs are strongly correlated with each other, but there are also groups of ability pairs that are less correlated with each other etc ...Typically, a pair of competency groups has a strong correlation with each other such as the ability to understand others and the combined ability group, the correlation level is 0.917 (corresponding to 91%). This result shows that, if the teacher being HYPO's personnel-in-charge has the ability to understand others well, it will be easier to form a group of abilities to coordinate with related forces in the organizational process to perform his or her own duties. In 06 competency groups of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge, the competency group No. 06 - the competency group in combination with related forces has a strong influence on the remaining competency groups. With high scores of 0.917, 0.688, 0.618, 0.683 and 0.719, respectively, they correspond to the competency group of ability to understand others, the competency group of ability to understand policy, the competency group of decision-making abilities, the competency group of ability to self-execution, HYPO's personnel-in-charge's work skills, the competency group to organize activities in HYPO's work and pupil's movements in schools, etc. In other words, if this competency group is formed, it will lead to competency groups to have better performance results. This result shows that if the teacher is a HYPO's personnel-in-charge, he is equipped and formed the competencies to coordinate with relevant forces in the process of performing tasks such as: knowing well the relevant forces, functions and tasks of HYPO's organization, the relationship and influence in the organization or the responsibilities and tasks for the HYPO's activities in the schools, etc. It will be very helpful for teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge to better perform their duties.

From the perspective of competencies theory, competency framework and social theories to build competencies, the competency framework of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge, we see that, when teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge to correctly identify the problem of their own responsibilities, the HYPO's functions in schools and the relationship with individuals (school leaders, teachers, ...) and other organizations (pedagogical council, Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union, ...) in the process of performing tasks and implementing the HYPO's work program and the pupil's movement in schools will be more easier. Ecosystem theory holds that every time an individual's problem (determining the task, job, understanding the policy, having the ability to perform the task, ...) is properly and appropriately determined then finding coordination with related organizations will be simpler and more effective. In summary, the results in Table 3.2 show that the 06 groups of competencies that have been researched have a close relationship, interact and have a high degree of mutual correlation.

4. Conclusion

The results of the study on the current competency status of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge are high, with this level, teachers initially have basic understanding of operation and can perform a

number of skills and careers and have a positive view of their professional activities. In addition, the results also show that the competencies of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge has a difference between 06 groups, in which the group with the ability to understand the policy has a high GPA score but the group with the ability to understand the policy has a high GPA score. The power to organize the HYPO's activities has a low GPA score. Study results confirm that 06 surveyed competencies have a close relationship with each other.

Given the current competency status of teachers being HYPO's personnel-in-charge is above and want teachers to meet the requirements of the new general education program in general and education in the current context requires administrators, therefore, the ministries and branches need to have solutions of both macro and micro scale to improve the competencies of performing tasks for the teaching staff who are HYPO's personnel-in-charge.

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